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Review Article

A REVIEW ARTICLE ON HYPERTENSIVE-CLONIDINE**R. Jona Methusala*, M. Noor Basha**

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Abstract:

Clonidine is an antihypertensive medication that acts on alpha-adrenergic and imidazoline receptor agonists. Clonidine is an antihypertensive drug that lowers blood pressure and heart rate by relaxing the arteries and increasing the blood supply to the heart; it has other FDA-approved indications such as treatment of attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) in children (FDA approval 2010); management of tics commonly found with Tourette syndrome; and adjunct therapy for severing cancer-related pain. This activity reviews the mechanism of action, adverse event profile, toxicity, dosing, pharmacodynamics, and monitoring of clonidine, pertinent for interprofessional team members when indicated for therapy.

Clonidine is a centrally active antihypertensive agent effective in the treatment of mild, moderate and severe hypertension, alone or in combination with other drugs. Use of oral clonidine has often been limited by side effects which include dry mouth and drowsiness. Transdermal clonidine was therefore developed as an alternative to oral therapy, while avoiding the potential for decreased efficacy associated with trough levels. The transdermal therapeutic system is a laminate consisting of an external film impermeable to moisture and to the drug, a thin layer of active drug dispersed within a highly drug-permeable matrix, a membrane with a controlled intrinsic permeability regulating the rate of delivery of drug to the skin, and an adhesive coating that attaches the system to the skin surface. The permeation of drug through the skin occurs primarily by diffusion. Maximum reduction in blood pressure occurs 2 to 3 days after initial application, and is maintained for at least 7 days or until the system is removed. The rate at which clonidine is presented to the skin surface is controlled by the microporous membrane: this rate is the same for all strengths of transdermal clonidine, the amount of clonidine released being proportional to its surface area. Thus, the daily dose is regulated by the area of skin covered. Typically, steady-state plasma concentrations are reached on the fourth day after initial transdermal system application. The lack of dose dependency in half-life and renal clearance estimates emphasize that the transdermal absorption of clonidine is linear. The plasma clonidine concentration produced by a particular transdermal dose varies considerably between individuals as a result of interindividual variation in renal clearance. For this reason, it is recommended that dosages be titrated up from the smallest system (3.5 cm²) until the desired pharmacological effect has been obtained.

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INTRODUCTION:

Clonidine is an antihypertensive medication that acts on alpha-adrenergic and imidazoline receptor agonists. Clonidine is an antihypertensive drug that

lowers blood pressure and heart rate by relaxing the arteries and increasing the blood supply to the heart;

it has other FDA-approved indications such as treatment of attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) in children (FDA approval 2010); management of tics commonly found with Tourette syndrome; and adjunct therapy for severing cancer-related pain. This activity reviews the mechanism of action, adverse event profile, toxicity, dosing, pharmacodynamics, and monitoring of clonidine, pertinent for interprofessional team

Clonidine:

Figure 1 clonidine structure

Mechanism of action:

Clonidine has an alpha-antagonist effect in the posterior hypothalamus and medulla. The final response is reduced sympathetic outflow from the central nervous system (CNS), which clinically causes a decrease in arterial blood pressure.

Pharmacokinetic data

Bioavailability : 70–80% (oral), [1][2] 60–70%

Protein binding : 20–40% [4]

Metabolism : Liver to inactive metabolites, [4] 2/3 CYP2D6 [8]

Onset of action : 30–60 minutes after an oral dose

Elimination half-life: IR: 12–16 hours; 41 hours in kidney failure, 48 hours for repeated dosing

Excretion : Urine (72%)

HISTORY:

In 1988 we first reported that in 71 smokers, clonidine was an aid in short-term cigarette smoking cessation. To our surprise, clonidine's effectiveness was From the Department of Clinical Psychopharmacology, New York State Psychiatric Institute, the Department of Psychiatry, College of Physicians and Surgeons, and the School of Public Health, Columbia University. Supported in part by grant DA04732 from the National Institute for Drug Abuse (Rockville, Md.), by an Established Investigator Award from the National Alliance for Research on Schizophrenia and Depression (New York, N.Y.), and by Suzanne C. Murphy (New York, N.Y.). Received for publication March 8, 1993; accepted July 19, 1993. Reprint requests: Alexander H. Glassman, MD, New York State We also noted that, among smokers coming to our clinic, histories of major depression were much more frequent than expected and that these histories of major depression were associated with failure to stop smoking. Since that report the association between major depression and cigarette smoking has been replicated in a number of as has the association with poor outcome in smoking cessation. We have recently published a meta-analysis of available reports on the efficacy of clonidine and found a significant benefit from the drug (odds ratio, 2.36; 95% confidence interval [CI], 1.69 to 3.28).¹⁰ However, the findings of the individual trials varied widely, and about half of the studies failed to find a significant drug effect. This report is a large-scale replication of our original study. It describes three hundred subjects enrolled in that protocol who have now completed 1 year of follow-up. ¹ Because the literature suggests that antidepressants may aid smoking cessation, current use of any antidepressant drug was an exclusion criterion.¹²

Subjects with histories of major depressive disorder had to have been free of symptoms for at least 6 months and to have taken no anti-depressant medication for at least 6 weeks. Medical examinations and laboratory tests were also performed, and subjects provided informed consent. At the second visit, all subjects who met the eligibility criteria posted a \$100 deposit, which was re-turned at the end of the 10-week protocol regardless of outcome. The therapist, in consultation with the physician, had the option of modifying both the daily dose (between 150 and 750 gm per day) and the dosing schedule. At the 10-week visit, abstinence status was evaluated by the smoker's own account and verified by means of a blood sample analyzed for

plasma cotinine concentration. After 10 weeks of treatment clonidine was withdrawn gradually to avoid rebound hypertension and anxiety. Subjects who stopped treatment or could not be contacted were counted as treatment failures. Follow-up data were collected with verification by serum cotinine levels 6 and 12 months after completion of treatment. Subjects were paid for these follow-up visits. The significance of an interaction between treatment and subject characteristics suggested in the bivariate analyses was tested by use of multiple logistic regression. The level of nicotine dependence was measured by the Fagerstrom Tolerance

~questionnaire¹¹ and number.

Gender. There was a propensity at 10 weeks that did not reach statistical significance for male smokers treated with placebo and behavioral counseling to do better than female smokers treated in a similar way (odds ratio, 1.92; 95% CI, 0.90 to 4.1 1), which continued at 1-year follow-up (odds ratio, 2.52; 95% CI, 0.86 to 7.33).

Discovery and development

- Clonidine was introduced in 1966. It was first used as a hypertension treatment under the trade name of Catapres.
- Clonidine was patented in 1961 and came into medical use in 1966. It is available as a generic medication. In 2020, it was the 75th most prescribed medication in the United States, with more than 9 million prescriptions.

INVESTIGATION:**patients and Methods:**

Two studies were conducted after approval of our institution's Ethics Committee and consent of the involved patients. Patients in each study were scheduled for abdominal, orthopedic, or urologic surgery. Patients with respiratory or cardiac failure were excluded from the study, as were patients previously given clonidine or other α_1 agonists. General anesthesia was induced with thiopental (5 mg/kg) or propofol (2 mg/kg) and fentanyl (10-15 mg). Atracurium (0.5 mg/kg) was administered to facilitate orotracheal intubation, and anesthesia was maintained with 50% N₂O in oxygen and isoflurane, enflurane, halothane, or propofol. After surgery, patients were transferred to the post anesthesia care unit.

Sixty ASA physical status 1 and 2 adult patients were included in the first study. Upon arrival in the post-

anesthesia care unit, shivering patients were assigned randomly to receive one of the three following treatments: intravenous bolus injection of isotonic saline, 150 mg clonidine, or 10 mg ketanserin. Only intense shivering, presenting as tremor of the head, jaw, and arms and associated with piloerection, was included in the study to avoid spontaneous disappearance of shivering during setup

Table 1. Demographics and Anesthetic Agents in the Three Groups of Study 1

	Isotonic Saline	Clonidine	Ketanserin
Age (yr) (mean \pm SD)	41 \pm 16	36 \pm 15	34 \pm 9
Gender: M/F	12/7	12/3	15/5
Isoflurane	5	3	7
Enflurane	11	11	11
Halothane	3	0	1
Propofol	0	1	1

and connection of the monitors and baseline measurements.

Forty patients shivering after surgery were allocated randomly to one of four groups (n = 10 in each group): intravenous saline (no clonidine) or 37.5, 75, or 150 μ g clonidine. The effect on shivering of each intravenous bolus was assessed by an observer blinded to patient allocation, 2 and 5 min after treatment, according to the following scale: 0 = no effect, 1 = partial inhibition, and 2 = total inhibition. Systolic arterial blood pressure, heart rate, and rectal temperature were recorded before and 5 and 60 min after the bolus injection. Time-dependent values were compared using the method of Zerbe." This technique allows one to test the hypothesis of the equality of response curves for two or more groups at multiple time points or during any time interval. Its criterion is distributed as a Snedecor I test whose degrees of freedom depend not only on the group sample sizes

but also on the time period chosen. Two tailed, unpaired Student's t test was used when appropriate. Log-rank test was used to compare the evolution of percentage of patients shivering in the three groups at each time. Results are reported as mean \pm SD; $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

Although clonidine acted significantly faster than ketanserin ($P < 0.05$), clonidine and ketanserin were equally effective 10 min after the bolus injection. At that time, the percentage of patients still shivering was 58%, 5%, and 7%, respectively, in the saline, ketanserin, and clonidine groups ($P < 0.05$; fig. 1). Before treatment, mean core temperature was similar in the three groups: saline $35.6 \pm 0.8^\circ\text{C}$, clonidine $35.5 \pm 0.6^\circ\text{C}$, and ketanserin $35.6 \pm 0.8^\circ\text{C}$. Rewarming, however, appeared somewhat slower in the clonidine group than in the patients given saline ($P = 0.056$), and body temperature was significantly lower in the clonidine group 30-120 min after treatment. The rate of core rewarming was similar among patients given saline and those given ketanserin (fig. 2). Systolic pressure and heart rate decreased significantly in each group (table 2), but the reductions in systolic arterial pressure and heart rate were greater in the patient's given clonidine than in those given saline ($P < 0.05$ and $P = 0.07$, respectively). Systolic arterial pressure decreased to less than 100 mmHg in only two patients given clonidine and one given ketanserin. Mean arterial pressure remained above 60 mmHg in all patients, and none required treatment for hypotension. Two patients given clonidine had heart rates between 45 and 50 beats/min, but for only one or two consecutive measurements. One patient given ketanserin maintained a heart rate near 48 beats/min from the 30-min measurement until the study concluded.

Figure 2 duration of shivering expressed

Fig. 1 Duration of shivering expressed as survival curves patient received an intravenous bolus of isotonic saline (IS)

,10 mg ketanserin (k, or 150 µg clonidine (c). $p < 0.01$ was considered a significant difference versus saline. $+p < 0.05$ was considered a significant difference versus ketanserin.

Figure 3 time after treatment

Fig. 2. Change in core temperature (mean \pm SEM) in shivering patients treated by an intravenous bolus of isotonic saline (4), 10 mg ketanserin (0), or 150 mg clonidine (@). SEMs of the K group were omitted for clarity (SEMs ranged from 0.05° to 0.12° C and were similar to SEMs of the two other groups). * $P < 0.05$ was considered a significant difference versus saline.

Study 2:

Morphometric characteristics and anesthetic techniques were similar in the four groups (table 3).

The effect of clonidine on shivering was dose-dependent. The 150-ug dose of clonidine stopped shivering in all the patients within 2 min. Two minutes after injection of 75 ug clonidine, shivering was abolished in seven patients and reduced in the three others. Within 5 min after treatment, all patients in this group stopped shivering. In contrast, 37.5 mg clonidine had no significant effect when compared to saline.

The decrease in mean arterial pressure was significantly greater after the administration of 75 and 150 ug clonidine than after saline or 37.5 g clonidine, but no significant differences were detected between the 75 and 150 mg groups. Heart rate did not differ significantly among the groups.

Historical approaches in drug development:

Indian system of traditional medicines like ayurveda:

In the beginning of the first millennium AD, there were three principal systems of medicine: Ayurveda, Greek and Chinese medicine. Their fundamental

attitude to the relationship of man and nature was more or less the same; but their explanations of the human body and its physiology, pathology and therapy differed in some ways. Of the three ancient systems of medicine, it would appear that Ayurveda emerged as a remarkably holistic approach both in its foundational ideas and therapeutic measures. The present article attempts to trace the roots of ancient methods of healing, including the traditional Indian systems - Ayurveda, Unani and Siddha.

Indian system of traditional medicines like Rasa sastra and the Siddha system:

Of the Indian medical trinity - Ayurveda, Unani and Siddha - Ayurveda has its roots in Vedic literature, while Unani, which is Greco-Arabic medicine, owes its origin to Central and West Asia. Neither of them, however had any alchemical undertone. The Siddha system was regional confined to Tamil Nadu and its adjoining areas among Tamil-speaking people. There is a proverb in Tamil that 'a physician is the son of an alchemist' (Subarea 1997). Around the fourth century AD, the seeds of a new thinking coupled with esoteric practices, but inspired by Chinese alchemy, began to sprout. In this respect the Kaya Kalpa method of the Siddha system (Velan 1963), presumed

to lead to a youthful state over a long span of one's life, is still being practiced. Both the Rasa Astra and Siddha system have now joined the mainstream of Ayurveda by adopting *mutatis mutandis* the fundamental principles of Ayurveda. The canvas of Ayurveda was wide, encompassing as it did plant and animal life in its totality, the Reserved being concerned with the former, while the Hastyayurveda, Asvayurveda and Governed with elephants, horses, and bovine animals respectively. Ayurveda, therefore, emerged as the science of life in its diverse forms, and its medicinal armamentarium largely comprised plant extracts but included some animal products too. Over the five decades since Indian independence, the three traditional systems of medicine - Ayurveda, Unani and Siddha - have made considerable progress in respect of their education and practical training. The Central Council for Research in these systems has been engaged in the scientific investigations and clinical trials, of several chosen traditional drugs like those which claim their efficacy in curing diseases like peptic ulcer, amoebic dysentery and hypertension. The results in some cases have been positive. It would, however, appear that such investigations are few and far between. More systematic investigations are indeed necessary if the traditional drugs are to be preferred to their counterparts of modern medicine. Some pharmaceutical firms have expanded their activities in this direction. In any case, the traditional systems of medicine continue to find markets in India and abroad.

Indian system of traditional medicines like unani:

The Greek medicine or the Hippocratic and later the Galenic system (Hippocrates being the prop under and Galen, its admirer) underwent improvement, modification and diligent systematization by Arabic medical writers. It was carried to Europe during the 11-13th centuries (Savage-Smith 1994). At the same time, with the coming into being of Muslim rule in India, the Greco-Arab medicine or unani made its debut into India: elements (Al-Arkin), temperament (Aliza), four humors (Al-Akhmat), organs (Al-Alda), vital spirit (Al-Arwah), faculties (Al-Quwa) and functions (Alfa). The Unani concept of elements is that of Empedocles (5th century BC) - earth, fire, water and air with their four primary qualities: hot, cold, dry and moist. While this postulate was made use of by Alexandrian alchemists, Hippocratic medicine viewed it in a different perspective. The viability of Indian five elements (four of this type and akasa) in the Ayurvedic matrix has been discussed before. Such an application of five elements towards the explanation of physiological processes is noted for its absence either in Greco- or in Greco-Arabic

medicine. In contradistinction to the triose of Ayurveda, Unani adopted four humors: (i) blood or sanguinous humor, (ii) bile or bilious den, (iii) phlegm or sarus and (iv) black-bile or atrabilious one. Like in Ayurveda, preventive medicine or self-health care is an important aspect of Unani system. Ibn Sina has defined medicine (tab) as the knowledge of the estates of the human body in health and decline in health; its purpose is to preserve and endeavor to restore it whenever it is lost. Unani physicians depend by and large on pulse-reading and the examination of urine and stools as the diagnostic indicators of a disease. But, as in Ayurveda, they take into consideration the whole personality of a patient in diagnosis and prescribe therapeutic procedure in terms of regimental, dietetic and pharmaco-therapy as well as surgery when needed. Medicated baths - cold for a normal person, and a hot one for certain ailments - are also important, according to Unani. Its material medica includes mostly herbal drugs, besides some of animal and mineral origin. The Guiliani concept of temperament has its own originality and even drugs are supposed to have their temperament, according to which they are classified. Unani made rapid strides and attained high status during the Mughal rule (1526-1707). There were many notable Hakims during this period, who left behind their medical treatises which have added a veneer of excellence to the Indian medical literature

Chinese medicine

The Chinese had developed a vibrant medical thought and practice in their own characteristic way. In earlier stages, around the 14th or 13th century BC, in the Shang dynasty, the curse of dead ancestors was believed to be the cause of ailments and they were to be appeased by offerings, prayers and incantations. The Shang culture did not believe in any pharmacology per se. Sorcerers were held in esteem because it was thought that they would be the communicators with the spirits of the dead. In course of time, the 'ancestral medicine' yielded place to 'demonic medicine' as a healing practice. In this process the use of Confucian ideas and the Taoists' esoteric principles and practices came to the fore, and a new healing system gradually came up in the context of the social and political changes that took place from time to time. Even so, the remnants of 'demonic medicine' did not lose their relevance as they were also in practice. But, healing by the use of drugs and a systematic material medica were by and large confined to Taoists who had their own speculations. Among them, from the point of view of Chinese medicine, the yin-yang theory, the five elements and what was called Qi, deserve special mention. Taoists also believed in alchemy. As a

result, mercury and its compounds, Sulphur, arsenic substances, mica and others also found their way into the Chinese medicine, though for realizing some esoteric goals like attaining immortality or a state of 'deathlessness' (Needham 1963). The Chinese theory of five 'elements' and the concept of yin- yang constitute, by and large, the foundation of Chinese medicine (Ware 1966). While there is some similarity between the Greek and the Indian postulates of five 'elements', the Chinese 'elements' are at variance with The Chinese had developed a vibrant medical thought and practice in their own characteristic way Pulse examination was another important diagnostic tool. Acupuncture involving vital centers was a specialty of Chinese treatment. The activities of body and mind, according to Chinese, go on because of the interaction of certain substances of vital character, which were a manifestation of what was called Qi, a primal entity both material (body) and nonmaterial (mind), gross and subtle. In its material aspects, Qi was believed to lie at the bottom of all the observed phenomena and their degrees of aggregation and dispersion. Qi, was therefore, a basic concept of Chinese philosophy and through it of its medicine inasmuch as it explained the inter-relatedness between the universe and man (microcosm and macrocosm), the natural force outside and the physiological processes inside.

New approaches in drug discovery:

Case report:

A 19-year-old female patient was brought to the emergency department (ED) via ambulance, 2 hours after an intentional polypharmacy overdose consisting of 7.9 mg of clonidine, 260 mg of lisdexamfetamine Di mesylate, and 260 mg of escitalopram. Her medical history included attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder, migraines, and borderline personality disorder. On initial review by paramedics, she was found to be hypertensive with a blood pressure (BP) 160/120 mmHg, heart rate (HR) 60 beats per minute (bpm), and a Glasgow Coma Scale

(GCS) score of 14 (E3V5M6). En route to the ED, she was noted to have a transient period of hypotension (BP 70/45 mmHg), which resolved without intervention before arrival. In ED, she reported fatigue, but denied any other symptoms including chest pain. On examination, her BP was 147/ 91 mmHg, HR 89 bpm, and GCS score 14 (E3V5M6) with unremarkable cardiovascular and neurological examinations. Her electrocardiogram (ECG) showed sinus rhythm (HR 78 bpm) with a QT interval of 360 milliseconds. Her pathology investigations including ethanol and paracetamol were within normal limits or undetectable. Following consultation with the local toxicology service, the patient was admitted under the medical team for prolonged observation because of the large amount of clonidine ingested and mental health review upon recovery.

Treatment:

Treatment Approximately 24.5 hours after overdose, she had a medical emergency team (MET) call for BP 87/48 mmHg (supine) with HR 81 bpm associated with postural light-headedness and diaphoresis, but this resolved without intervention. A review later that day (29 hours after overdose) found her to be pale with ongoing diaphoresis. She reported postural dizziness, with BP 89/67 mmHg (supine) and BP 66/41 mmHg (standing). A repeat ECG showed a QT interval of 520 milliseconds (HR 78 bpm). Electrolytes were optimized, and given her autonomic instability, midodrine 5 mg TDS (3 time

per day, at 6 AM, 8 AM, and 10 AM) was planned to commence the following day. That evening, however, she had another MET call for hypotension (66/41 mmHg, sitting) with HR of 78 bpm, and her ECG showed a QT of 560 milliseconds (Fig. 1). Following liaison with the intensive care unit (ICU) and the department of cardiology, the patient was recommenced on telemetry, given 500 mL.

Figure 1. Twelve lead electrocardiogram (ECG) showing prolongation of QT interval. Twelve lead ECG taken approximately 30 hours after overdose showing a sinus heart rate of 78 beats per minute and a QT interval of 560 milliseconds.

Figure 4: sample treatment

was altered to 95 mmHg over the preceding 12 hours. Midodrine was successfully weaned before hospital discharge. On follow-up, the patient remains well and has had no further health concerns. Discussion Clonidine overdose is typically associated with altered conscious state, hypotension, and bradycardia due to its central presynaptic stimulation of α_2 receptors and α_2 receptor activation in the locus coeruleus. [1,6] In large overdoses, transient early hypertension can be seen because of mild stimulation of peripheral postsynaptic α_1 receptors.[7] Although these effects are well-documented, published data on the outcomes of larger overdoses with

Figure 2. Trend in hemodynamics from presentation to discharge. Trend of heart rate and systolic blood pressure from admission to discharge over time, noting MET calls for hypotension, pre-MET calls for chest pain, administration of IV fluid and initiation of midodrine. The single dose of metoprolol administered before CT coronary angiogram is also highlighted. CT, computed tomography; IV, intravenous; MET, medical emergency team.

Figure 5 hours post ingestion

respect to prolonged symptoms is limited. Our patient experienced prolonged orthostatic autonomic symptoms (postural hypotension, dizziness, diaphoresis) despite clinical euolemia, which prohibited discharge from hospital beyond 100 hours after ingestion. This has been our experience for prior cases of large clonidine overdoses and hence the hypothesis that midodrine may assist in symptom management and decreasing length of hospital stay. This further suggests that midodrine was efficacious in stabilizing her BP and improving symptoms despite underlying instability that was

only unmasked after the introduction of a β -blocker. This is contrary to the alternative possibility that the patient was recovering of their own accord, further supporting the argument for the potential benefit of midodrine.[11] Although she responded to naloxone after deterioration in her conscious state, she subsequently developed an anteroseptal myocardial infarction in association with a hypertensive crisis, and subsequent cardiac catheterization did not show any stenosis or occlusion of her coronary circulation. The authors concluded that in high doses clonidine can stimulate peripheral.

Figure 3. Trend in systolic blood pressure after initiation of midodrine. Trend of systolic blood pressure from initiation of midodrine to discharge, noting MET call for hypotension, pre-MET calls for chest pain, administration of IV fluid and the single dose of metoprolol administered before CT coronary angiogram given. CT, computed tomography; IV, intravenous; MET, medical emergency team.

Figure 6 trend in systolic blood pressure and midodrine

α_1 and α_2 adrenoreceptors leading to vasoconstriction, and this may have been the etiology of the myocardial infarction.[11] The duration of this effect with high doses has been described as being transient, so it is difficult to draw an association in our case given the occurrence of the NSTEMI in contrast to the time of ingestion. The case highlights several findings of importance with respect to the management of clonidine toxicity. First, the duration of autonomic instability can last several days before patients are able to mobilize appropriately. Further more, each author certifies that this material or similar material has not been and will not be submitted to or published in any other publication. The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author, Rotella JA, upon reasonable request. Funding None. Ethical approval of studies and informed consent This study was approved by the Northern Health Research Ethics Committee (March 29, 2022), and written informed consent was obtained from the patient. All authors have read the manuscript and approved its submission to the journal. This manuscript has the consent of the patient for the use of her data and for the publication of the data that The committee for the purpose of control and supervision of experiments on animals (CPCSEA) Guidelines for the care and use of laboratory:

Animals:

Good Laboratory Practices (GLP) for animal facilities is intended to assure quality maintenance and safety of animals used in laboratory studies while conducting biomedical and behavioral research and testing of products.

GOAL:

The goal of these Guidelines is to promote the humane care of animals used in biomedical and behavioral research and testing with the basic objective of providing specifications that will enhance animal wellbeing, quality in the pursuit of advancement of biological knowledge that is relevant to humans and animals.

VETERINARY CARE:

Adequate veterinary care must be provided and is the responsibility of a veterinarian or a person who has training or experience in laboratory animal sciences and medicine. Daily observation of animals can be accomplished by someone other than a veterinarian; however, a mechanism of direct and frequent communication should be adopted so that timely and accurate information on problems in animal health, behavior, and well-being is conveyed to the attending veterinarian. The veterinarian can also contribute to the establishment of appropriate policies and

procedures for ancillary aspects of veterinary care, such as reviewing protocols and proposals, animal husbandry and animal welfare; monitoring occupational health hazards containment, and zoonosis control programs; and supervising animal nutrition and sanitation. Institutional requirements will determine the need for full-time or part-time or consultative veterinary services

QUARANTINE, STABILIZATION AND SEPARATION:

Quarantine is the separation of newly received animals from those already in the facility until the health and possibly the microbial status of the newly received animals have been determined. An effective quarantine minimizes the chance for introduction of pathogens into an established colony. A minimum duration of quarantine for small lab animals is one week and larger animals is 6 weeks (cat, dog and monkey) Effective quarantine procedures should be used for non-human primates to help limit exposure of humans to zoonotic infections. Regardless of the duration of quarantine, newly received animals should be given a period for physiologic, psychologic and nutritional stabilization before their use. The length of time stabilization will depend on the type and duration of animal transportation, the species involved and the intended use of the animals. Physical separation of animals by species is recommended to prevent interspecies disease.

DISEASE SURVEILLANCE, DIAGNOSIS,

TREATMENT, AND CONTROL:

All animals should be observed for signs of illness, injury, or abnormal behavior by animal house staff. As a rule, this should occur daily, but more-frequent observations might be warranted, such as during postoperative recovery or when animals are ill or have a physical deficit. It is imperative that appropriate methods be in place for disease surveillance and diagnosis (Annexure 1 and 2). Unexpected deaths and signs of illness, distress, or other deviations from normal health condition in animals should be reported promptly to ensure appropriate and timely delivery of veterinary medical care. Animals that show signs of a contagious disease should be isolated from healthy animals in the colony. If an entire room of animals is known or believed to be exposed to an infectious agent (e.g., Mycobacterium tuberculosis in non-human primates), the group should be kept intact and isolated during the process of diagnosis, treatment, and control. Diagnostic clinical laboratory may be made available

ANIMAL EXPERIMENTATION INVOLVING HAZARDOUS AGENTS:

Institutions should have policies governing experimentation with hazardous agents. Institutional Biosafety Committee whose members are knowledgeable about hazardous agents are in place in most of the higher-level education, research institutes and in many pharmaceutical industries for safety issues. This committee shall also examine the proposal on animal experiments involving hazardous agents in addition to its existing functions (Annexure

– 8). Since the use of animals in such studies requires special consideration, the procedures and the facilities to be used must be reviewed by both the Institutional Biosafety Committee and Institutional Animal Ethics Committee (IAEC).

DURATIONS OF EXPERIMENTS:

No animal should be used for experimentation for more than 3 years unless adequate justification is provided

PHYSICAL RESTRAINT OF ANIMALS FOR EXAMINATION:

Brief physical restraint of animals for examination, collection of samples, and a variety of other clinical and experimental manipulations can be accomplished manually or with devices be suitable in size and design for the animal being held and operated properly to minimize stress and avoid injury to the animal. Prolonged restraint of any animal, including the chairing of non-human primates, should be avoided unless essential to research objectives. Less restrictive systems, such as the tether system or the pole and collar system, should be used when compatible with research objectives. The following are important guidelines for the use of restraint equipment's: Restraint devices cannot be used simply as a convenience in handling or managing animals. The period of restraint should be the minimum required to accomplish the research objectives. Animals to be placed in restraint devices should be given training to adapt to the equipment. Provision should be made for observation of the animal at appropriate intervals. Veterinary care should be provided if lesions or illness associated with restraint are observed. The presence of lesions, illness, or severe behavioral change should be dealt with by the temporary or permanent removal of the animal from restraint.

FUNCTIONAL AREAS OF ANIMAL HOUSE:

The size and nature of a facility will determine whether areas for separate service functions are possible or necessary. Sufficient animal area is required to: ensure separation of species or

isolation of individual projects when necessary to receive, quarantine, and isolate animals and to provide for animal housing. In facilities that are small, maintain few animals or maintain animals under special conditions (e.g., facilities exclusively used for housing germfree colonies or animals in runs and pens) some functional areas listed below could be unnecessary or included.

PHYSICAL FACILITIES OF ANIMAL HOUSE:

(a) Building materials:

should be selected to facilitate efficient and hygienic operation of animal facilities. Durable, moisture-proof, fire-resistant, seamless materials are most desirable for interior surfaces including vermin and pest resistance.

(b) Corridor(s):

Should be wide enough to facilitate the movement of personnel as well as equipment's and should be kept clean.

(c) Utilities such as water lines, drain pipes and electrical connections should preferably be accessible through service panels or shafts in corridors outside the animal rooms.

(d) Animal room doors

Doors should be rust, vermin and dust proof. They should fit properly within their frames and provided with an observation window. Door closures may also be provided. Rodent barriers can be provided in the doors of the small animal facilities.

(e) Exterior windows

Windows are not recommended for small animal facilities. However, where power failures are frequent and backup power is not available, they may be necessary to provide alternate source of light and ventilation. In primate rooms, windows can be provided.

(f) Floors

Floors should be smooth, moisture proof, nonabsorbent, skid-proof, resistant to wear, acid, solvents, adverse effects of detergents and disinfectants. They should be capable of supporting racks, equipment, and stored items without becoming gouged, cracked, or pitted, with minimum number of joints. A continuous moisture-proof membrane might be needed. If sills are installed at the entrance to a room, they should be designed to allow for convenient passage of equipment.

(g) Drains

Floor drains are not essential in all rooms used exclusively for housing rodents. Floor in such rooms can be maintained satisfactorily by wet vacuuming or

mopping with appropriate disinfectants or cleaning compounds. Where floor drains are used, the floors should be sloped and drain taps kept filled with water or corrosion free mesh. To prevent high humidity, drainage must be adequate to allow rapid removal of water and drying of surfaces.

(h) Walls and ceilings

Walls should be free of cracks, unsealed utility penetrations, or imperfect junctions with doors, ceilings, floors and corners. Surface materials should be capable of withstanding scrubbing with detergents and disinfectants and the impact of water under high pressure

(i) Storage areas:

Separate storage areas should be designed for feed, bedding, cages and materials not in use. Refrigerated storage, separated from other cold storage, is essential for storage of dead animals and animal tissue waste. Facilities for sanitizing equipment and supplies an area for sanitizing cages and ancillary equipment is essential with adequate water supply.

(j) Experimental area:

All experimental procedures in small animals should be carried out in a separate area away from the place where animals are housed. For larger animal functional areas for aseptic surgery should include a separate surgical support area, a preparation area, the operating room or rooms, and an area for intensive care and supportive treatment of animals.

ENVIRONMENT:

(a) Temperature and humidity control:

Air conditioning is an effective means of regulating these environmental parameters for laboratory animals. Temperature and humidity control prevents variations due to changing climatic conditions or differences in the number and kind of room occupants. Ideally, capability should be provided to allow variations within the range of approximately 18 to 29°C (64.4 to 84.2°F), which includes the temperature ranges usually recommended for common laboratory animals. The relative humidity should be controllable within the range of 30% to 70% throughout the year. For larger animals a comfortable zone (18 to 37°C) should be maintained during extreme summer by appropriate methods for cooling.

(b) Ventilation:

In renovating existing or in building new animal facilities, consideration should be given to the

ventilation of the animals' primary enclosures. Heating, ventilating, and air-conditioning systems should be designed so that operation can be continued with a standby system. The animal facility and human occupancy areas should be ventilated separately.

(c) Power and lighting:

The electrical system should be safe and provide appropriate lighting and a sufficient number of power outlets. It is suggested that a lighting system be installed that provides adequate illumination while people are working in the animal rooms and a lowered intensity of light for the animals. Fluorescent lights are efficient and available in a variety of acceptable fixtures. A time-controlled lighting system should be used to ensure a regular diurnal lighting cycle wherever required. Emergency power should be available in the event of power failure.

(d) Noise control:

The facility should be provided with noise free environment. Noise control is an important consideration in designing an animal facility. Concrete walls are more effective than metal or plaster walls in containing noise because their density reduces sound transmission.

ANIMAL HUSBANDRY:

(A) Caging or housing system:

The caging or housing system is one of the most important elements in the physical and social environment of research animals. It should be designed carefully to facilitate animal well-being, meet research requirements, and minimize experimental variables. The housing system should:

- provide space that is adequate, permit freedom of movement and normal postural adjustments, and have a resting place appropriate to the species; (Annexure – 3)
- provide a comfortable environment
- provide an escape proof enclosure that confines animal safety
- provide easy access to food and water;
- provide adequate ventilation
- meet the biological needs of the animals, e.g., maintenance of body temperature, urination, defecation and reproduction the animals dry and clean, consistent with species requirements
- facilitate research while maintaining good health of the animals. They should be constructed of sturdy, durable materials and designed to minimize cross-infection between adjoining units. Polypropylene, polycarbonate and stainless-steel cages should be used to house small lab animals, Monkeys should be housed in cages made of steel or painted mild steel and for other animals such as sheep, horses, the details can be seen in Annexure – 3. To simplify servicing and sanitation, cages should have smooth,

impervious surfaces that neither attract nor retain dirt and a minimum number of ledges, angles, and corners in which dirt or water can accumulate. The design should allow inspection of cage occupants without disturbing them. Feeding and watering devices should be easily accessible for filling, changing, cleaning and servicing. Cages, runs and pens must be kept in good condition to prevent injuries to animals, promote physical comfort, and facilitate sanitation and servicing. Particular attention must be given to eliminate sharp edges and broken wires, keeping cage floors in good condition.

(B) sheltered or outdoor housing:

When animals are maintained in outdoor runs, pens, or other large enclosures, there must be protection from extremes in temperature or other harsh weather conditions and adequate protective and escape mechanism for submissive animals, as in case of monkeys by way of an indoor portion of a run, should be provided. Shelter should be accessible to all animals, have sufficient ventilation, and be designed to prevent buildup of waste materials and excessive moisture. Houses, dens, boxes, shelves, perches, and other furnishings should be constructed in a manner and made of materials that allow cleaning or replacement in accordance with generally accepted husbandry practices when the furnishings are soiled or worn-out. Ground-level surfaces of outdoor housing facilities can be covered with absorbent bedding, sand, gravel, grass, or similar material that can be removed or replaced when needed to ensure appropriate sanitation. Buildup of animal waste and stagnant water should be avoided for example, by using contoured or drained surface. Other surfaces should be able to withstand the elements and be easily maintained.

(C) Social environment:

The social environment includes all interactions among individuals of a group or among those able to communicate. The effects of social environment on caged animals vary with the species and experience of the animals. In selecting a suitable social environment, attention should be given to whether the animals are naturally territorial or communal and whether they will be housed singly or in groups. When appropriate, group housing should be considered for communal animals. In grouping animals, it is important to take into account population density and ability to disperse; initial familiarity among animals; and age, sex, and social rank. Population density can affect reproduction, metabolism, immune responses, and behavior. Group composition should be held as stable as possible, particularly for canine, non-human primates, and

other highly social mammals, because mixing of groups or introducing new members can alter behavioral and physiological functions. Non-human primates should have a run for free ranging activities. Food: Animals should be fed palatable, non-contaminated, and nutritionally adequate food daily unless the experimental protocol requires otherwise. Feeders should allow easy access to food, while avoiding contamination by urine and feces. Food should be available in a amount sufficient to ensure normal growth in immature animals and maintenance of normal body weight, reproduction, and lactation in adults. Food should contain adequate nutrition, including formulation and preparation; freedom from chemical and microbial contaminants; bio-availability of nutrients should be at par with the nutritional requirement of the animal. Laboratory animal diets should not be manufactured or stored in facilities used for farm feeds or any products containing additives such as rodenticides, insecticides, hormones, antibiotics, fumigants, or other potential toxicants. Areas in which diets are processed or stored should be kept clean and enclosed to prevent entry of insects or other animals. Precautions should be taken if perishable items such as meats, fruits, and vegetables are fed, because these are potential sources of biological and chemical contamination and can also lead to variation in the amount of nutrients consumed. Diet should be free from heavy metals (e.g., lead, arsenic, cadmium, nickel, mercury), naturally occurring toxins and other contaminants. Exposure to extremes in relative humidity, unsanitary conditions, light, oxygen, and insects hasten the deterioration of food. Meats, fruits, vegetables, and other perishable items should be refrigerated if required to be stored. Unused, open food should be stored in vermin – proof condition to minimize contamination and to avoid potential spread of disease agents. Food hoppers should not be transferred from room to room unless cleaned and sanitized. The animal feed should contain moisture, crude protein, essential vitamins, minerals, crude fat and carbohydrate for providing appropriate nutrition.

WATER:

Ordinarily animals should have continuous access to fresh, potable, uncontaminated drinking water, according to their particular requirements. Periodic monitoring of microbial contamination in water is necessary. Watering devices, such as drinking tubes and automatic waterers if used should be examined routinely to ensure their proper operation. Sometimes it is necessary to train animals to use automatic watering devices. It is better to replace water bottles than to refill them, however, if bottles are refilled,

care should be taken that each bottle is replaced on the cage which it was removed.

BEDDING:

Bedding should be absorbent, free of toxic chemicals or other substances that could injure animals or personnel, and of a type not readily eaten by animals. Bedding should be used in amounts sufficient to keep animals dry between cage changes without coming into contact with watering tubes. Bedding should be removed and replaced with fresh materials as often as necessary to keep the animals clean and dry. The frequency is a matter of professional judgement of the animal care personnel in consultation with the investigation depending on the number of animals and size of cages. However, it is ideal to change the bedding twice a week. The desirable criteria for rodent contact bedding are ammonia binding, sterilizable, deleterious

products not formed as a result of sterilization, easily stored, non-desiccating to the animal, uncontaminated, unlikely to be chewed or mouthed, non-toxic, no malodorous, nestable, disposable by incineration, readily available, remains chemically stable during use, manifests batch uniformity, optimizes normal animal behavior, non-deleterious to cage-washers, non-injurious and non-hazardous to personnel, no nutritious and non-palatable. Nesting materials for newly delivered pups wherever can be provided (e.g., paper, tissue paper and cotton).

SANITATION AND CLEANLINESS:

Sanitation is essential in an animal facility. Animal rooms, corridors, storage spaces, and other areas should be cleaned with appropriate detergents and disinfectants as often as necessary to keep them free of dirt, debris, and harmful contamination. Cleaning utensils, such as mops, pails, and brooms, should not be transported between animal rooms. Where animal waste is removed by hosting or flushing, this should be done at least twice a day. Animals should be kept dry during such procedures. For larger animals, such as dogs, cats, and non-human primates, soiled litter material should be removed twice daily. Cages should be sanitized before animals are placed in them. Animal cages, racks, and accessory equipment's, such as feeders and watering devices, should be washed and sanitized frequently to keep them clean and contamination free. Ordinarily this can be achieved by washing solid bottom rodent cages and accessories once or twice a week and cages, racks at least monthly. Wire – bottom rodent cages for all other animals should be washed at least every 2 weeks. Where hazardous biological, chemical, or physical agents are used, a system of

equipment monitoring might be appropriate. Deodorizers or chemical agents other than germicidal should not be used to mask animal odors. Such products are not a substitute for good sanitation.

WASTE DISPOSAL:

Wastes should be removed regularly and frequently. All waste should be collected and disposed of in a safe and sanitary manner. The most preferred method of waste disposal is incineration. Incinerators should be in compliance with all central, state, and local regulations. Waste cans containing animal tissues, carcasses, and hazardous wastes should be lined with leak-proof, disposable liners. If wastes must be stored before removal, the waste storage area should be separated from other storage facilities and free of flies, cockroaches, rodents, and other vermin. Cold storage might be necessary to prevent decomposition of biological wastes. Hazardous wastes should be rendered safe by sterilization, contamination, or other appropriate means before they are removed from an animal facility for disposal.

RECORD KEEPING:

Training record of staff involved in animal activities
 • Water analysis report
 The animal house should maintain the following records:
 • Animal house plans, which includes typical floor plan, all fixtures etc.
 • Animal house staff record-both technical and non-technical
 • Health record of staff/ animals
 • All standard operating procedures (SOPs) relevant to the animals
 • Breeding, stock, purchase and sales records
 • Minutes of institute Animals Ethics Committee Meetings
 • Records of experiments conducted with the number of animals used (copy of Form D)
 • Death Record
 • Clinical record of sick animals

PERSONNEL AND TRAINING:

The selection of animal facility staff, particularly the staff working in animal rooms or involved in transportation, is a critical component in the management of an animal facility. The staff must be provided with all required protective clothing (masks, aprons, gloves and gumboots and other footwear) while working in animal rooms. Facilities should be provided for change over with lockers, wash basin, toilets and bathrooms to maintain personal hygiene. It is also important a regular medical check-up is arranged for the workers to ensure that they have not picked up any zoonotic infection and also that they are not acting as a source of transmission of infection to the animals. The animal house in-charge should ensure that

persons working in animal house do not eat, drink, smoke in animal room and have all required vaccination, particularly against tetanus and other zoonotic diseases. Initial in-house training of staff at all levels is essential. A few weeks must be spent on the training of the newly recruited staff, teaching them the animal handling techniques, cleaning of cages and importance of hygiene, disinfection and sterilization. They should also be made familiar with the activities of normal healthy and sick animals so that they are able to spot the sick animal during their daily routine checkup of cages (Annexure – 7).

ANAESTHESIA AND EUTHANASIA:

The scientists should ensure that the procedures, which are considered painful, are conducted under appropriate anesthesia as recommended for each species of animals. It must also be ensured that the anesthesia is given for the full duration of experiment and at no stage the animal is conscious to perceive pain during the experiment. If at any stage during the experiment the investigator feels that he has to abandon the experiment or he has inflicted irreparable injury, the animal should be sacrificed. Neuromuscular blocking agents must not be used without adequate general anesthesia (Annexure – 5). In the event of a decision to sacrifice an animal on termination of an experiment or otherwise, an approved method of euthanasia should be adopted (Annexure – 6) and the investigator must ensure that the animal is clinically dead before it is sent for disposal. The data about large animals, which have been euthanized, should be maintained.

Anesthesia:

Unless contrary to the achievement of the results of study, sedatives, analgesics and anesthetics should be used to control pain or distress under experiment. Aesthetic agents generally affect cardiovascular, respiratory and thermo-regulatory mechanism in addition to central nervous system. Before using actual anesthetics, the animal is prepared for anesthesia by overnight fasting and using pre-anesthetics, which block parasympathetic stimulation of cardio-pulmonary system and reduce salivary secretion. Atropine is the most commonly used anticholinergic agent. Local or general anesthesia may be used, depending on the type of surgical procedure. Local anesthetics are used to block the nerve supply to a limited area and are used only for minor and rapid procedures. This should be carried out under expert supervision for regional infiltration of surgical site, nerve blocks and for epidural and spinal anesthesia. A number of general aesthetic agents are used in the form of inhalants. General anesthetics are also used in the form of

intravenous or intramuscular injections such as barbiturates. Species characteristics and variation must be kept in mind while using anaesthetic. Side effects such as excessive salivation, convulsions, excitement and disorientation should be suitably prevented and controlled. The animal should remain under veterinary care till it completely recovers from anesthesia and postoperative stress. Euthanasia: is resorted to events where an animal is required to be sacrificed on termination of an experiment or otherwise for ethical reasons. The procedure should be carried out quickly and painlessly in an atmosphere free from fear or anxiety. For accepting a euthanasia method as humane it should have an initial depressive action on the central nervous system for immediate insensitivity to pain. The choice of a method will depend on the nature of study, the species of animal to be killed (Annexure – 6). The method should in all cases meet the following requirements: (a) Death, without causing anxiety, pain or distress with minimum time lag phase. (b) Minimum physiological and psychological disturbances. (c) Compatibility with the purpose of study and minimum emotional effect on the operator. (d) Location should be separate from animal rooms and free from environmental contaminants. Tranquilizers have to be administered to larger species such as monkeys, dogs and cats before a euthanasia procedure.

Preclinical study:

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Animals' Equal numbers of male and female Sprague-Dawley rats weighing between 250 and 350 g (Harlan Laboratories, Indianapolis, IN) were co-housed with ad libitum access to food and water. Rats were maintained on a 12 h light/dark cycle. All experiments were performed during the light (day) phase. All procedures were approved by McGill Animal Care Committee and complied with the Canadian Council for Animal Care guidelines. Drugs Clonidine hydrochloride (Sigma-Aldrich, Canada) was dissolved in sterile saline (0.9% NaCl) to the final concentration (50, 100, or 200 mg/kg) and administered intraperitoneally at a volume of 1 ml/kg (Galeotti et al, 2004). Behavioral Procedure Rats underwent auditory fear conditioning, reactivation, and testing in the same experimental chamber to further resemble, in our animal model, a PTSD-like intrusive memory in which cue and context are usually not easily separated. The conditioning chamber consisted of a brightly lit plexiglass box (25 x 29 x 29 cm) with stainless steel-grid floor that was enclosed within a sound attenuating box (Coulbourn Instruments, Whitehall, PA).

Experiment 1. Rats were first habituated to the chamber for 5 min on 2 consecutive days. The following day (day 1), rats were conditioned. Conditioning involved 2 min of acclimation to the chamber after which rats received a single pairing of a tone (30 s, 5 kHz, 75 dB) terminating with a foot shock (1 s, 0.75 mA). Rats remained in the chamber an additional minute before being returned to their home cages. On day 2, the fear memory was reactivated by placing the animals in the experimental chamber and presenting the tone without the shock. Rats were then removed from the context and clonidine (50, 100, or 200 mg/kg) or its vehicle was administered immediately. On days 3 and 10, animals were tested for post reactivation long-term memory (PRLTM) with the presentation of a single tone. Experiment 2. No reactivated controls were habituated and trained as in experiment 1, but rats did not receive the reactivation and instead remained in the animal colony where they received the clonidine treatment on day 2. Experiment 3. As a post reactivation short-term memory (PR-STM) control, animals were habituated, trained, reactivated, and given post reactivation clonidine as in experiment 1 half minutes of acclimation to the chamber, rats received a single pairing of a different frequency tone (20 s, 3 kHz, 85 dB) terminating with a foot shock (1 s, 1.1 mA). Rats remained in the chamber an additional 2 min before being returned to their home cages. Experiment 5. Rats were habituated, trained, and reactivated as described in experiment 1. However, rats underwent reactivation on days 2, 3, and 4, each time followed by an injection of clonidine (100 mg/kg) or its vehicle. Rats were tested on days 5 and 12 using the same procedure as above. Behavior was recorded using Freeze View software (Acidimetries). Freezing, defined as immobilization except for respiration (Blanchard and Blanchard, 1969), was the conditioned response taken as a measure of fear memory retention. Scores are presented as the percentage of time spent freezing during the total duration of the tone.

Experiment 1: Post reactivation Administration of Clonidine Impairs Reconsolidation of Auditory Fear Memories in a Dose-Dependent Manner: post hoc tests indicated significant differences between the clonidine treated group and the controls at both memory retent administered systemically at 50, 100, or 200 mg/kg. We conditioned the animals on day 1 and reactivated them the following day by exposing them again to the conditioning chamber and the tone. After reactivation, animals received an injection of clonidine or its vehicle and were tested for memory We evaluated whether clonidine is effective at disrupting fear memory reconsolidation when retention a day later. To establish if the effects of clonidine were long lasting, rats were also tested again on day 10 (Figure 1a). Clonidine was effective at blocking memory reconsolidation at all tested doses, and its effect was long lasting as the memory impairment was still observed a week after the treatment (Figure 1b–d). A repeated-measures ANOVA revealed a main effect of treatment ($F(1, 34) = 6.08, p < 0.05$ for 50 mg/kg; $F(1, 48) = 10.61, p < 0.01$ for 100 mg/kg; $F(1, 37) = 47.99, p < 0.01$ for 200 mg/kg) and day ($F(2, 68) = 9.09, p < 0.001$ for 50 mg/kg; $F(2, 96) = 36.04, p < 0.001$ for 100 mg/kg; $F(2, 74) = 22.05, p < 0.0001$ for 200 mg/kg). A significant treatment day interaction was observed for 100 mg/kg ($F(2, 96) = 4.66, p < 0.05$) and 200 mg/kg ($F(2, 74) = 5.71, p < 0.01$). Subsequent Fisher's tests (for 50 mg/kg, $p < 0.05$ for both tests; for 100 mg/kg, $p < 0.001$ for PR-LTM and $p < 0.01$ for PR-LTM 2; for 200 mg/kg, $p < 0.001$ for PRLTM and $p < 0.01$ for PR-LTM 2). In addition, significant freezing decreases were observed within the clonidine group between reactivation and both PR-LTM performances (for 50 mg/kg, $p < 0.05$; for 100 mg/kg, $p < 0.001$; for 200 mg/kg, $p < 0.001$). Taken together, the present data suggest that clonidine disrupted fear memory reconsolidation in a dose-dependent manner. Clonidine reached its maximum effect at 100 mg/kg, as increasing the dose further did not lead to a greater impairment of the conditioned response in the treated group.

Figure 1 Postreactivation administration of clonidine impairs reconsolidation of auditory fear memories. (a) Schematic of the experimental design. Rats received a single systemic injection of clonidine or its vehicle immediately after a reactivation session, and were tested for postreactivation long-term memory 1 day (PR-LTM) and 1 week later (PR-LTM 2). A dose of (b) 50 µg/kg ($n = 20$), (c) 100 µg/kg ($n = 25$) and (d) 200 µg/kg ($n = 20$) was effective at impairing memory reconsolidation compared with the vehicle group (respectively, $n = 16$, $n = 25$, and $n = 20$) as shown by an impaired conditioned response (freezing) at both time points. Bars represent mean \pm SEM freezing to the tone. Markers represent the mean \pm SEM freezing before the onset of the tone. Statistical significance: * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$.

Figure 7 Postreactivation administration

Experiment 2: Reconsolidation Blockade by Clonidine Is Selective to Reactivated Fear Memories:

We assessed whether the effect of clonidine on reconsolidation was dependent on memory reactivation. We injected clonidine at a dose of 100 mg/kg 24 h after training without exposing the animals to the conditioning chamber and tone. Rats were tested for memory retention on days 3 and 10 (Figure 2a). No significant effect of clonidine (repeated measures ANOVA, $F(1, 22) = 0.002$, $p > 0.05$) was observed in the absence of reactivation, as compared with the vehicle-injected group 1 day and 1 week after receiving the treatment (Figure 2b). In addition, a repeated-measures ANOVA showed no significant effect of day ($F(1, 22) = 1.34$, $p > 0.05$) and no treatment day interaction ($F(1, 22) = 0.39$, $p > 0.05$). Thus, clonidine disrupts reconsolidation of an auditory fear memory only when administered following reactivation of that memory.

Figure 8 Reconsolidation blockade

Figure 2 Clonidine does not impair retention of nonreactivated fear memories. (a) Schematic of the experimental design. Rats received a single systemic injection of clonidine (100 µg/kg) or its vehicle without a memory reactivation session and were tested for long-term memory retention 1 day (LTM) and 1 week later (LTM 2). (b) Clonidine-treated rats ($n = 12$) showed a similar conditioned response (freezing) to the vehicle group ($n = 12$) when tested 24 h or 1 week after injection. Bars represent mean \pm SEM freezing to the tone. Markers represent the mean \pm SEM freezing before the onset of the tone.

Figure 3 Postreactivation administration of clonidine does not impair short-term fear memories. (a) Schematic of the experimental design. Rats received a single systemic injection of clonidine (100 µg/kg) or its vehicle immediately after a reactivation session and were tested 4 h later for postreactivation short-term memory (PR-STM) and 1 day later for postreactivation long-term memory (PR-LTM). (b) Clonidine-treated rats ($n = 12$) showed a similar conditioned response (freezing) to the vehicle group ($n = 9$) when tested 4 h after reactivation, but reduced freezing behavior 1 day after injection. Bars represent mean \pm SEM freezing to the tone. Markers represent the mean \pm SEM freezing before the onset of the tone. Statistical significance: *** $p < 0.001$.

Figure 9: schematic of the experimental design

Figure 4 Postreactivation administration of clonidine does not impair the ability to learn new fear memories. (a) Schematic of the experimental design. After receiving a postreactivation injection of clonidine (200 µg/kg) or vehicle, and being tested for memory retention 1 day (PR-LTM) and 1 week later (PR-LTM 2), rats were conditioned to fear a different tone using a different auditory fear protocol. (b) Rats that previously received clonidine ($n = 12$) showed intact fear behavior (freezing) compared with the vehicle-treated animals ($n = 12$) when tested 1 day (test 1) or 1 week later (test 2). Bars represent mean \pm SEM freezing to the tone. Markers represent the mean \pm SEM freezing before the onset of the tone.

Figure 10 clonidine does not impair short term fear memories.

BIOSTATISTICS AND PRECLINICAL STUDIES:

Ten patients with idiopathic restless leg syndrome (RLS) were asked to rate their symptoms at baseline during 2 weeks of placebo and 2 weeks of clonidine treatment by using a four-point scale. On two consecutive nights of each treatment period, polysomnography (PSG) and studies were performed. Patients subject reported improvement in leg sensations ($p = 0.02$) and motor restlessness ($p = 0.001$) while receiving clonidine (mean = 0.5 mg/day). On PSG testing, sleep onset occurred faster with clonidine (12 minutes) compared with placebo (30 minutes) and baseline (47 minutes) ($p = 0.006$). Adverse findings associated with clonidine treatment included decreased percent REM sleep in the clonidine group (4%) compared with placebo (16%) and baseline (16%) ($p = 0.001$) and increased REM latency in the clonidine group (195 minutes) compared to the placebo (70 minutes) and baseline groups (89 minutes) ($p = 0.028$). There were no significant changes in total sleep time, stage 1 and 2 sleep, sleep efficiency, awakenings, arousals or periodic limb movements in sleep. This syndrome is usually idiopathic and often familial (8), but secondary forms of RLS are often associated with conditions such as gastrectomy (2), diabetes mellitus (2), uremia (9), vascular insufficiency (10), anemia (II) and caffeine abuse (12). Some secondary forms are associated with peripheral neuropathy or radiculopathy. Patients with secondary forms of RLS may respond differently to treatment than do patients with idiopathic RLS; thus, it is important to distinguish the type of RLS a patient has when selecting patients for studies. Current treatment of RLS includes monotherapy or downloaded from <https://academic.oup.com/sleep/article/19/1/52/2749779> by guest on 14 October 2023 53 poly therapy with carbidopa/levodopa (Sinemet®), dopamine agonists, opioids or benzoxiquine.

METHODS:

Patient selection Patients signed the Institutional Review Board approved informed consent form and were selected from patients evaluated at the Department of Neurology clinic at Robert Wood Johnson University Hospital, New Brunswick, NJ, and the Veterans Administration Medical Center, Lyons, NJ. All patients exhibited the following four symptoms of RLS: (a) paresthesia's, (b) motor restlessness, both of which worsen at (c) night and (d) rest (lying or sitting). All patients experienced subjective complaints of sleep disturbances such as difficulty with sleep onset and maintenance or excessive daytime somnolence. Patients were not

required to have periodic limb movements of sleep (PLMS). Patients with uncontrolled hypertension [systolic blood pressure (SBP) > 160 mm Hg, diastolic blood pressure (DBP) > 100 mm Hg], hypotension (SBP < 90 mm Hg, DBP < 60 mm Hg), bradycardia <60 bpm), secondary forms of RLS due to peripheral neuropathy or radiculopathy, history of drug abuse, sleep apnea or allergy to clonidine were excluded from the study. Patient unable to discontinue RLS medications because of intolerable worsening of RLS symptoms were also excluded from the study.

DESIGN:

The study was a randomized, double-blind, placebo controlled, 3-period, crossover trial. For a period of at least 3 days before the study, all patients were gradually tapered off of all medications that could affect RLS symptoms (for example Levodopa, dopamine agonists, benzodiazepines, opioids, baclofen, carbamazepine or tricyclic antidepressants). Patients did not receive any RLS medications for at least 2 days before the baseline PSG studies. We did not adjust any of the medications prescribed for other purposes, and attempts were made to keep them constant throughout the study. The first period consisted of a 4-day baseline period, during which no RLS medications were taken. The next two periods were 2-3 weeks in length depending on scheduling. Before each of these periods, patients were randomized to receive clonidine Dosing Clonidine and matching placebo tablets were provided by Boehringer Ingelheim (PD 1172, PD0915, respectively). The investigators telephoned patients daily to assess signs and symptoms and to adjust dosages. If patients experienced an exacerbation of RLS symptoms or adverse medication effects during the dose titration phases, their dose was adjusted up or down or their dosing interval was adjusted accordingly. Compliance was assessed by counting the returned number of tablets at the end of each treatment period.

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